

Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD). with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD) " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD) based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD), namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD), both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Regional Development Bank; Sharia BPD; Library Research

Introduction

One of the financial institutions that has an important role in the country's economy is banks, banks function as financial intermediary institutions. The existence of banks provides many benefits with the products they offer in supporting the country's economy (Mukti & Suprayogi, 2019). Not only conventional-based banks, currently Sharia banking in Indonesia is experiencing very rapid growth because it has been proven to be able to withstand economic shocks, especially during the global crisis (Wiranatakusuma, 2017).

One of the banks in Indonesia, namely the Regional Development Bank, Regional Development Bank (BPD) is one of the national banking industries that shows good performance efficiency in order to support regional development. Regional Development Bank (BPD) has a Sharia Business Unit (UUS) and there are 16 Sharia Business Units owned by BPD Bank registered with Bank Indonesia(Puspita & Shofawati, 2017).

Research on Regional Development Banks (BPD) has increased every year. From 2013 to 2022, on the garuda.kemdikbud.go.id page there are 421 scientific publications discussing Conventional BPD Banks, and 8 scientific publications discussing Sharia BPD Banks.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD). library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD), so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD), both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Regional Development Banks (BPD) in Law Number 13 of 1962 are banks established in Level I Private Areas which aim to provide financing for the implementation of regional development efforts under the framework of the Universal National Development Plan (Putranto, 2018).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD). The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD) " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD) based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Regional Development Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 25 topics related to the financial performance of Regional Development Banks, namely:

1. First, the influence of market risk, credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR, Net Interest Margin/ NIM, Loan to Asset Ratio /LAR, leverage, financial quality, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, inflation, interest rates credit, Third Party Funds/DPK, exchange rates, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, Equity to Assets Ratio /EAR, Non-Performing Loans/ NPL, macroeconomics, market share expansion strategy, bank characteristics, and Quality of Productive Assets/KAP to profitability/ Return On Assets / ROA.
2. Second, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR, retail credit, and credit interest rates on interest income.
3. Third, the influence of risk profile, Good Corporate Governance/ GCG, Return On Assets/ ROA, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Net Interest Margin /NIM, Operational Costs on Operational Income/BOPO, Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR, Minimum Statutory Reserve/GWM, Non Performing Loans/ NPL, Fee Based Income, E-Banking transactions, bank health, and credit growth towards profits.
4. Fourth, the influence of the Dividend Discounted Model /DDM and Price Earning Ratio /PER on initial share valuation.
5. Fifth, the influence of productive asset growth on operational performance.
6. Sixth, the influence of Third Party Funds/DPK, Non-Performing Loans /NPL, and loan interest rates on the distribution of working capital, investment and consumption credit.
7. Seventh, the influence of asset growth, Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Non Performing Loans / NPL, Return On Assets / ROA, Operational Costs on Operating Income / BOPO, Minimum Statutory Reserves / GWM, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, credit market share, interest rates deposit insurance interest, credit risk, risk aversion, and opportunity cost on Net Interest Margin / NIM.
8. Eighth, measuring company efficiency using Data Envelopment Analysis /DEA and Stochastic frontier.
9. Ninth, the influence of market structure, credit risk, liquidity, macroeconomic level and operational efficiency on bank performance.
10. Tenth, the influence of company performance on provincial GRDP.
11. Eleventh, the effect of implementing Asset-Liability Management / ALMA on liquidity risk.
12. Twelfth, the influence of Non Performing Loans / NPL, Operational Costs on Operating Income / BOPO, Return On Assets / ROA, inflation, liquidity, profitability, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, Net Open Position in Foreign Exchange / NOPFE on Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR.
13. Thirteenth, the influence of profitability, liquidity, leverage, company size and institutional ownership on financial statement disclosure.
14. Fourteenth, efficiency level using Data Envelopment Analysis /DEA.
15. Fifteenth, company performance uses tax planning and the Balanced Scorecard approach.
16. Sixteenth, the bank's health level uses RGEC, Chow/Hausmen Test, RBBR, and CAMEL.
17. Seventeenth, Fee Based Income analysis, short term capabilities, and Non-Performing Loans /NPL.

18. Eighteenth, financial performance uses financial ratios, Good Corporate Governance/ GCG, CAMEL, RGEC, PEARLS, and intellectual capital methods.
19. Nineteenth, the influence of financial performance on company value and dividend policy.
20. Twentieth, the influence of concentration, company size, and inflation on stability.
21. Twenty-first, the influence of board size, age diversity, distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR, interest rates, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, risk disclosure, grant accounting recognition, and gender diversity on performance/reports finance.
22. Twenty-second, the influence of inflation, interest rates, Debt to Equity Ratio /DER), Debt to Asset Ratio /DAR, Return on Assets /ROA, and Return on Equity /ROE on stock prices.
23. Twenty-third, the influence of board size, digital transformation, and ownership structure on company performance.
24. Twenty-fourth, the effect of dividend announcements on price changes, abnormal returns, stock trading volume and after dividend distribution.
25. Twenty-fifth, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR, Non-Performing Loans /NPL, Net Interest Margin /NIM, inflation, intellectual capital, capital structure and company size on financial performance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Regional Development Bank Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 50 topics related to the performance of Regional Development Bank employees, namely:

1. Online attendance.
2. Management audit.
3. Human resources accounting.
4. Organizational culture.
5. Workload.
6. Work discipline.
7. Superior support.
8. Work facilities.
9. Transactional and situational leadership styles.
10. Good Corporate Governance /GCG.
11. Human resources scorecard.
12. Organizational climate.
13. Leadership.
14. Occupational Health and Safety/3K.
15. Job satisfaction.
16. Ability to apply technology.
17. Competence.
18. Communication.
19. Organizational commitment of permanent employees and outsourcing.
20. Work-family conflict.
21. Individual characteristics.
22. Emotional and spiritual intelligence.
23. Creativity.
24. Loyalty.

25. Work environment.
26. Work motivation.
27. Spiritual motivation.
28. On and off the job training.
29. Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR orientation
30. Quality of Work Life / QWL.
31. The selection of outstanding funding officers uses the profile matching method.
32. Person organization fit.
33. Work experience.
34. Job promotion.
35. Career development.
36. Use of accounting information technology.
37. Employee knowledge.
38. Financial knowledge.
39. Financial behavior.
40. Income.
41. Work training.
42. Accounting information system.
43. Internal control system.
44. Management Control System/SPM.
45. Attitude.
46. Competency standards.
47. Work stress.
48. Self-efficacy.
49. Level of education.
50. Work life balance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Customer Behavior of Regional Development Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 29 topics related to the behavior of Regional Development Bank customers, namely:

1. Automated Teller Machine /ATM.
2. Marketing mix.
3. Company image.
4. Customer Relationship Management /CRM.
5. Corporate image.
6. Internal service quality/inservequal.
7. Internet banking.
8. Trust.
9. Commitment.
10. Marketing communications.
11. Service quality.
12. Product quality.
13. Ease of use.
14. Financial literacy.
15. Benefit.
16. Mobile banking.
17. Cashier service.
18. Mobile- based problem reporting using the Flutter framework.
19. Customer service service.

20. Personal selling.
21. Public relations.
22. Promotion.
23. Relationship marketing.
24. Marketing strategy (value proposition).
25. core banking system uses the Technology Acceptance Model /TAM.
26. The customer service information system uses the Queuning System method.
27. Website- based E-Samsat transaction reporting information system.
28. Word of Mouth.
29. Risk tolerance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Regional Development Bank Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 26 research topics related to Regional Development Bank financing products, namely:

1. First, the influence of debtor characteristics, interest rates, supervision, credit term, credit ceiling, debtor age, collateral, credit installments, economic sector, and income on the level of repayment of financing credit.
2. Second, the influence of Loan to Value, Third Party Funds/TPF, 5C credit assessment, credit quality, credit term, credit marketing policy, supervision, accounting information, non-accounting information, income level, business capability, debtor characteristics, repayment capacity, performance finances, and the number of dependents on the decision to grant financing credit.
3. Third, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, Net Interest Margin / NIM, inflation, BI rate, Gross Domestic Product / GDP, company size, Operational Costs on Operating Income / BOPO, credit granting strategy, Covid-19 19, and economic growth towards non-performing/ non-performing loans /NPL.
4. Fourth, the influence of internal control systems, procedures and prudential banking on credit granting control.
5. Fifth, the influence of management concern, loans received, Third Party Funds/DPK, credit interest rates, inflation, Loan to Deposit Ratio/ LDR, Non-Performing Loans/ NPL, Net Interest Margin/ NIM, and exchange rates on credit distribution.
6. Sixth, transition from permanent working capital credit to general credit.
7. Seventh, a decision support system for granting credit using the TOPSIS method.
8. In the future, analyze the positioning of working capital credit products.
9. Ninth, credit agreement with the application of the grosse deed as an acknowledgment of debt and article 1320 Jo 1338 of the Civil Code.
10. Tenth, implementation of People's Business Credit/KUR distribution in the MSME sector and its impact.
11. Eleventh, solving bad credit problems.
12. Twelfth, default through subrogation.
13. Thirteenth, the influence of Gross Regional Domestic Product/GRDP and inflation on consumer credit demand.
14. Fourteenth, restructuring of problem/bad loans.
15. Fifteenth, the influence of credit distribution, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Non-Performing Loans /NPL on interest income.

16. Sixteenth, guarantees/collateral, in the form of pension letters, village apparatus decrees, and CPNS decrees.
17. Seventeenth, productive credit accounting systems and procedures.
18. Eighteenth, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio /LDR and Non-Performing Loans/ NPL on credit volume.
19. Nineteenth, procedures for disbursement of People's Business Credit/KUR.
20. Twentieth, the influence of Bank Indonesia/PBI regulations on total credit, credit ratios, risk, efficiency and profitability in MSMEs.
21. Twenty-first, legal protection of the interests of debtors and creditors in credit agreements.
22. Twenty-second, the influence of Non-Performing Loans /NPL on the level of credit collectibility.
23. Twenty-third, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Return on Assets / ROA, Return on Equity / ROE, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, and Net Interest Margin / NIM on Non-Performing Loans / Net and Gross NPL.
24. Twenty-fourth, the influence of Sharia Business Unit/UUS risk management, efficiency, and non-performing loans on working capital financing.
25. Twenty-fifth, dispute resolution through arbitration.
26. Twenty-sixth, the role of the notary in financing letters.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Regional Development Bank Savings Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 5 research topics related to Regional Development Bank savings/savings products, namely:

1. First, the effect of savings on Third Party Funds/DPK.
2. Second, the effect of profit sharing/ratio on the amount of Mudharabah deposit funds.
3. Third, the influence of the Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, inflation, and Bank Indonesia/SBI Certificate interest rates on term deposit interest rates.
4. Fourth, management of savings products.
5. Fifth, the application of the Mudharabah Muthlaqah agreement to savings.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues in Regional Development Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 27 research topics related to issues at Regional Development Banks, namely:

1. First, the influence of audit committee characteristics on bank supervision.
2. Second, solvency analysis of the bank.
3. Third, the supervision mechanism of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS.
4. Fourth, legal resolution of the issuance of blank checks.
5. Fifth, bank liability due to failure of the clearing transfer system.
6. Sixth, the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR on company brand preferences and other impacts.
7. Seventh, comparison of the performance of state-owned banks and BPD.

8. Eighth, structure conduct performance / SCP analysis based on asset value and fund value.
9. Ninth, pension fund payment procedures.
10. Tenth, implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR, Return On Assets /ROA, Good Corporate Governance/ GCG, digitalization transformation, and money transfer costs.
11. Eleventh, legal protection for customers in transactions, in the form of internet banking.
12. Twelfth, the tax rate structure in looking at corporate taxpayer compliance.
13. Thirteenth, socialization and education of students about the benefits of products and services.
14. Fourteenth, the influence of the Deposit Insurance Corporation/LPS on moral hazard behavior.
15. Fifteenth, consumer protection against the use of standard clauses regarding the granting of power of attorney in bank credit agreements.
16. Sixteenth, setting the maximum limit for capital participation.
17. Seventeenth, implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR towards community empowerment.
18. Eighteenth, withholding, depositing and reporting Income Tax/PPh.
19. Nineteenth, manpower supply strategy with SWOT analysis.
20. Twentieth, empowering the role of women.
21. Twenty-first, issuance of performance bonds.
22. Twenty-second, the influence of environmental uncertainty and business strategy on the quality of accounting information systems.
23. Twenty-third, prevention of money laundering crimes.
24. Twenty-fourth, Islamic green banking.
25. Twenty-fifth, use of Letter of Credit /L/C using internet banking in international trade transactions.
26. Twenty-sixth, implementation of PSAK 71.
27. Twenty-seventh, company development by spin-off.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD), namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; and (6) Other issues.

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